

SENTIMENT AND PERCEPTIONS ABOUT HPV VACCINE IN INDIA: EVIDENCE FROM SOCIAL MEDIA

AUTHORS

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Executive summary:

Cervical cancer is the 2nd most common cancer in India, despite being largely preventable through HPV vaccination. Since 2008, the HPV vaccine has been available in the Indian market; however, vaccine acceptance and awareness remain low. This policy brief summarizes the findings of a qualitative study among Indian Reddit users discussing HPV vaccination, aiming to understand public perceptions and sentiments towards it. The study explored Reddit users' attitudes, information gaps, and barriers affecting vaccine uptake using the 5A model—Access, Affordability, Awareness, Acceptance, and Activation. The codes most commonly associated with negative and positive sentiments were analyzed using a tree cum heat map.

Study findings revealed the majority had neutral or positive sentiment towards the HPV vaccination, with only 20.4% reporting negative sentiments. High cost, safety concerns, misinformation, limited access, and cultural factors were the key factors found to be frequently associated with negative sentiments. In contrast, factors such as right knowledge about the HPV vaccine, healthcare worker (HCW) recommendations, personal health beliefs, and past experiences were found to be associated with positive sentiments.

These findings highlight the need for strategic digital communication that incorporates evidence-based insights to address the lack of information about different brands, eligibility criteria, misinformation about the lack of efficacy, side effects, and concerns about vaccines manufactured in India, while remaining considerate of cultural factors.

5. Acceptance gap: Key issues identified that lowered vaccine acceptance were:

- a) Fear of side effects
- b) Lower perceived risk because of being in a monogamous relationship
- c) Misconceptions that it is not effective post sexual exposure
- d) Misconception that the Indian vaccine Cervavac lacks efficacy as compared to other global brands.
- e) Misconception that it causes infertility
- f) Cultural stigma associated with STDs
- g) Mistrust of the health system, with concern about the pharmaceutical profit motive
- h) Peer and healthcare worker recommendations improved acceptance of the vaccine.
- i) Social media acted as both an enabler and a barrier to vaccine uptake. A celebrity event increased awareness and prompted many to take the vaccine, but it also fueled conspiracy theories.

Policy implications and recommendations:

1. Prioritise affordability and access: The Government must launch the vaccine under the national immunisation schedule to make the vaccine affordable. Along with hospitals, HPV vaccination can be introduced in school-based programs to increase access.

2. Public awareness should be raised through targeted, evidence-based information by delivering culturally appropriate messages that address

- a) Age and eligibility criterion
- b) Vaccination schedule
- c) Male vaccination
- d) Safety and efficacy evidence (especially of the Indian vaccine)
- e) Myths about sexual activity and infertility

3. Leverage peripheral healthcare workers to build confidence in HPV vaccination: frontline healthcare workers need to be trained to dispel myths and misconceptions about HPV vaccination and to create momentum in vaccine uptake.

4. Social media to dispel misinformation: In the digital age, it is necessary to monitor emerging rumors and to counter them at the source. Digital creators can

collaborate with medical influencers to provide evidence-based information

5. Cultural stigma around STDs: School programs and village health & sanitation nutrition days can be used to dispel stigma surrounding STDs and to promote the HPV vaccine as a cancer-preventing tool, which can spread through multiple ways.

Further Information

Full study: Perceptions and sentiments associated with HPV vaccine uptake among Indian Reddit users: a qualitative social media analysis, BMC Public Health (2025)

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References:

1. Key data on HPV and HPV-related cancers [Internet]. Available from: https://hpcvcentre.net/statistics/reports/IND_FS.pdf
2. Thomson A, Robinson K, Vallée-Tourangeau G. The 5As: A practical taxonomy for the determinants of vaccine uptake. Vaccine [Internet]. 2016 Feb;34(8):1018–24. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0264410X15017466>
3. Bashar MDA, Khan IA. Introduction of HPV vaccine in universal immunization programme of India: A step in the right direction for the elimination of cervical cancer. Indian Journal of Cancer. 2024 Jul;61(3):638–40.
4. Singh G, Dash NR, Shaju A, Chakkalakkunnan SS. Perceptions and sentiments associated with HPV vaccine uptake among Indian Reddit users: a qualitative social media analysis. BMC Public Health. 2025 Nov 19;25(1):4037.